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MOTIVATIONAL STIMULI IMPROVE WINGATE TEST PARAMETERS IN ROWERS

Dea Karaba Jakovljević, Danijel Slavić, Damir Lukač, Miodrag Drapšin, & Otto Barak

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Abstract

Motivation is fundamental component of success in sport. Positive social environment can influence and modulate motivation state of athletes involved in different sport activities. In this investigation verbal encouragement as motivation factor was administered to rowers during Wingate anaerobic test. The aim of the study was to explore whether verbal encouragement as a motivational stimuli affects the parameters of Wingate anaerobic test (anaerobic power, anaerobic capacity and slope of power) in athletes. Investigated group consisted of 30 rowers (age: 18.9 ± 2.28 years; height: 186 ± 3.23 cm; body mass: 85.8 ± 6.45 kg). All subjects performed Wingate test twice-with and without verbal encouragement from the beginning of the test. Test parameters were recorded and statistically analysed. Results show increase of parameters of Wingate test when performed with verbal encouragement: Anaerobic power (754W vs. 801W); Slope of power (112W/s vs. 132W/s); and Anaerobic capacity (14.6kJ vs. 16.2kJ) were higher when test was administered with verbal encouragement. Verbal encouragement when administered as loud verbal commands has been shown to increase anaerobic parameters of Wingate test athletes, and has potential of improving sport performance.

Keywords: athletes, physical activity, muscle strength.